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Project-based funding for green energy technology by the Korean Green Mission and its changes and characteristics

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Introduction

The government has become active in stimulating research and innovation activities and steering their directions to deal with policy objectives (Braun, 2003; Whitley, 2007, 2014). In particular, as global level challenges such as climate change are positioned at the center of the policy agenda, calls and expectations to align knowledge production with efforts to solve these complex problems in contemporary society are growing stronger. Many countries are prioritizing particular areas relevant to these issues and intensifying support for research targeting them. Project-based funding is one of the ways to implement this, by incorporating national strategies and policy goals into funding programs and establishing various procedures for setting priorities, allocating resources, and evaluating outcomes to ensure the contribution of research outcomes.

In particular, funding schemes for ‘mission-oriented’ programs are used as a direct means to guide research activities in line with government policies. Mission-oriented innovation aims to reorient the direction of research and innovation to contribute to solving societal problems, resulting in a significant level of concentration of public resources towards the goals of missions (Larrue, 2021). And since these missions go beyond the spheres of science or innovation policy, they involve broad participation of a diverse set of actors, and thus investment is also made broadly across sectors, not particular public or private entities (Wanzenböck et al., 2020).

The Green Growth was a mission launched in 2008 by the Lee Myung-bak (hereafter MB) administration (2008-2013) of South Korea to respond to climate change and achieve economic growth. In a situation where climate change and the global financial crisis in 2008 have emerged as global problems, the government emphasized that green industries and new business opportunities will be shaped through “green transformation” (Presidential Committee on Green Growth, 2009). Fostering research and innovation to develop economically feasible technical solutions for the green industrialization became one of the important goals of the mission, and the government selected “27 core green technologies” directly connected to the industrial sectors to be strategically invested in (Korean Government Ministries Concerned, 2009). The

government expected to produce results that could contribute to the mission—industrialization of green technology—through R&D programs in these technological fields.

The purpose of this study is to trace how the funding for the areas targeted by the Green Growth mission has changed. And since investment in prioritized areas is made across government agencies rather than specific R&D programs, mission-related funding needs to be approached at the level of the government's overall R&D expenditure. To this end, this study will analyze the green technology-related funding provided by the Korean government, and focus on 8 technology fields under the energy generation technology category: silicon-based solar cell, non-silicon based solar cell, bioenergy, fast reactor, light water reactor, nuclear fusion, hydrogen energy, and fuel cell.

While investment is intensified, each government ministry as a funder and each research organization has different priorities based on their respective functions and roles, so this will make a difference in the characteristics of funding and research activities; this difference is also made by various characteristics of each technology field and the readiness level and expectations for industrialization as well as duration of government pursued the mission. By considering these elements, it will help to comprehensively understand funding according to the mission.

Data and Method

Data on Korean funding for green energy technology and research outcomes

This study uses data on the Korean government funding provided by the National Science & Technology Information Service (NTIS), which manages records of all government projects as well as their research outcomes. The dataset for this study is based on the records of projects from 1999 to 2018, Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) paper outcomes, and patent outcomes from 2007 to 2017.

The NTIS project record contains title, abstract, keywords in Korean and English, funder, organization the principal investigator is affiliated with, budget, etc. The unique identifier of each project is linked to records of paper and patent outcomes.

The bibliographic information of paper outcomes was acquired from the CWTS in-house version of the Web of Science (WoS). By comparing WoS records including paper titles, journals, DOIs, etc. with NTIS paper outcomes records, 575,081 cases (98.3%) of bibliographic information were matched.

Method for searching projects and papers

Korean projects and papers on green energy technology were retrieved through the following procedure. First, search strings were constructed based on terms uniquely used in each technology field and their combinations. For example, “tokamak” is used only in the nuclear fusion field, so it can be included as is in search strings. In contrast, as “photovoltaic” and “solar cell” are terms used in both silicon-based and non-silicon-based solar cells, they can be used as search strings only if they are combined with terms related to specific fields such as “amorphous silicon” or “perovskite”. The glossary for green energy technology was constructed through a review of technical literature and expert advice. The search strings are composed of Korean and English to search Korean projects as well as bibliographic information of papers in the WoS, but due to differences in language and expression, they are not completely identical.

Next, Korean search strings were applied to records of title, abstract, and keywords in the NTIS database to retrieve a list of projects funded for research on green energy technology. And to supplement this result, a list of projects was retrieved using codes describing the National Science and Technology Classification System and the Green Technology Classification System. However, due to the inconsistency of these codes, they were only complementary and could not be fully relied upon. Records of 26,363 projects between 2005 to 2018, 63,708 papers, and 30,416 patent outcomes from 2007 to 2017 were retrieved.

Finally, all papers on green energy technology were searched by applying English search strings to the title and abstract records of the WoS database. A total of 690,725 papers from 2000 to 2020 were retrieved. It was used as a reference to compare whether the contents of funded papers were related to green energy technologies.

Findings

Overall trends in funding

The size of funding for green energy technology and its share in the total government research funding has changed along with the Green Growth mission. Its scale increased sharply with the launch of the mission, peaking at 1,405.5 billion KRW (9.5% of the total) in 2011, and has declined with the end of the mission. This is because the active investment was made through the strong policy will in the first year of the government that proposed the Green mission, and its momentum was not maintained in the last year of the government. And the mission and prioritized funding had to be stopped as it was replaced by the next government's agenda.

Figure 1: Government funding for R&D projects of green energy technology.

Funding for all green energy technology increased and decreased with the term of the MB administration, but the trend was slightly different for each field. The most notable change existed in the silicon and non-silicon solar cell fields, where the size of funding increased by 676% and 801% respectively from 2007 to 2011 peak. Although the size of investment decreased after the MB administration, it is still larger than when the mission was launched. On

the other hand, despite investment in the hydrogen energy and fuel cell fields increased during the mission, only 92.5% and 84% of investment was made in 2014 compared to 2007– both fields use hydrogen or hydrogen compounds to generate electricity.

In terms of funding per project, the scale of nuclear energy research was larger than other fields. Funding for research on fast reactor, light water reactor, and nuclear fusion averaged 950.8, 837.6, and 1170.5 million KRW per project, more than double the size of other green energy technology fields; fast reactor and light water reactor fields had more than double their median than other fields. This was because projects related to the installation, modification, and maintenance of large-scale facilities and equipment were also funded as nuclear energy research.

The NTIS database applies the typology of R&D activity classified by the Frascati Manual of the OECD to projects: basic research, applied research and experimental development (OECD, 2015). Overall, the proportion of basic research in projects has gradually increased from 26.9% in 2007 to 45.3% in 2018. However, the proportion of the three types was different for each field. In the case of solar cell fields, the proportion of development was high in silicon-based, whereas the proportion of basic and applied research was high in non-silicon-based: silicon solar cells have already been widely used and improving the efficiency is the main focus of research, while non-silicon solar cells have not yet reached the stage of commercialization.

In the case of nuclear energy fields, light water reactor had a high proportion of development projects because its main goal was to improve the performance of currently operating reactors; the fast reactor had a low proportion of development as it still needs more research to be commercialized; nuclear fusion had a significantly higher proportion of projects not classified in the three types, mainly for large-scale infrastructure.

Funding by organization

The Ministry of Science and Technology takes the largest proportion of government R&D expenditure, and about half of the funding for green energy technology was also provided by them. However, during the MB administration which pursued the industrialization of green technology, the proportion of funding from the Ministry of Industry increased: after peaking at 55.3% in 2010 from 34.4% in 2007, it decreased again to 34.7% in 2012. Basic research in the Ministry of Science and Technology and development projects in the Ministry of Industry had the highest share of funding.

Figure 2: Proportion of funds by the ministry.

The proportion of universities in funding continued to increase mainly for basic research, while the proportion of government-funded research institutes (GRIs) decreased: from 11.9% and 53.5% in 2007 to 26.2% and 42.2% in 2018 respectively. However, considering that the proportion of universities and GRIs in total R&D funding was 23.0% and 42.4% in 2007, and 22.9% and 40.7% in 2018, it can be said that funding for green energy technology also showed a tendency to approach the average.

Figure 3: Proportion of funds by the research organization.

The funding patterns were different for each field. In the case of silicon solar cell, the Ministry of Industry was the main funder and provided about 3/4 of the funding; companies received more than half of the funding for development projects. On the other hand, the proportion of development in non-silicon solar cell research was not as high as that of silicon solar cell, and companies were not the main recipients. This difference was due to the commercialization mentioned above.

In the case of nuclear energy, most of the funding for fast reactor and nuclear fusion research was for GRIs: the Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute and the Korea Institute of Fusion Energy are public research organizations specialized in nuclear research. Although the Ministry of Science and Technology is the main funder for these two areas, the proportion of funding from the Ministry of Industry also increased temporarily during the MB administration.

Development projects accounted for a high proportion of funding for light water reactor research, while funding to universities was insignificant. The Ministry of Science and Technology provided about three-quarters of the funding for light water reactor research before the mission, but the proportion of the ministry of industry increased and accounted for about three-quarters during the MB administration, and is higher after the mission. This was because the policy focus shifted to the industrialization and export of light water reactors, which are being operated based on the established design.

Research outputs

The research results of green energy technology showed an overall trend of increase in quantity and proportion. The number and proportion of publications continued to increase, from 1,104 and 6.1% in 2007 to 6,713 and 17.3% in 2017. Patent outputs also increased continuously from 679 in 2007 to 5,676 in 2017. Universities accounted for 79.3% of the paper outcomes, and the Ministry of Science and Technology accounted for 88.4% as a funder; 62% of paper outcomes were funded for basic research, 22% for applied research, and 8.8% for development projects. 45.5% of patent outcomes received funding for basic research, 23.9% for applied research, and 26% for development projects; 44.8% were registered by universities, 33.7% by GRIs, and 14.9% by companies; 65.4% were funded by the Ministry of Science and Technology and 29.1% were by the Ministry of Industry 29.1%.

Figure 4: Distribution of funding by type of project and organization.

Figure 5: Paper outcomes of funded projects.

Relevance of paper outcomes to the mission

To achieve the goal of the mission, the research topics of funded papers should be relevant to the development of green energy technology. This study checked whether funded papers were included in the list of papers retrieved from the WoS by search strings. Of the total of 51,164 funded papers, 9,894 (19.3%) were on the list. In other words, only 9,894 papers included terms for green energy technology, which were used to construct search strings in this study, in the titles or abstracts. By research organization, 19.4%, 28.8%, and 44.6% of funded papers published by universities, GRIs, and companies were in the list of papers retrieved from the WoS.

The proportion of funded papers containing green energy technology terms was lower at each technology level. This was because some projects and their paper outcomes had different research topics. For example, if a project funded for silicon solar cell publishes a paper on non-silicon solar cell, it is counted as green energy technology at the aggregate level, but not as research on silicon solar cell at the level of individual technology.

Table 1. Funded Korean papers matched with papers retrieved from WoS.

Area	Number of funded papers	Papers matched with WoS
Silicon solar cell	5,096	458 (9.0%)
Non-silicon solar cell	18,729	3,382 (18.1%)
Bioenergy	11,481	1,403 (12.2%)
Fast reactor	1,259	213 (16.9%)
Light water reactor	1,396	135 (9.7%)
Nuclear fusion	2,887	481 (16.7%)
Hydrogen energy	8,606	656 (7.6%)
Fuel cell	14,254	1,975 (13.9%)
Total	51,164	9,894 (19.3%)

To complement this result, 96 random samples were picked and checked whether they are related to green energy technology (confidence level of 95% with a sampling error of 10%). 21

papers (21.9%) were directly related to green energy technology, but the rest were indirectly related or unclear. However, it cannot be said that these are irrelevant to green energy technology: theoretical research on nuclear physics is not directly related to the development of nuclear energy technologies but may contribute indirectly.

Discussions and future work

This study examined how the Green Growth mission of the Korean government which aimed at industrializing green technology affected research funding. Funding for green energy technology and its proportion increased between 2008 and 2012, the period of the Lee Myung-bak government that promoted the mission, and decreased thereafter. At that time, the proportion of funding by the ministry of industry increased temporarily due to the objectives of the mission. It was also observed that mission-related funding was discontinued as a political agenda stopped.

And the type of project was in part influenced by the mission. Funding for applied research and development projects increased during the mission. In particular, funding for development projects and companies significantly increased in fields that have already been commercialized, such as silicon solar cell and light water reactor.

Although funding decreased after the mission, the number of publications continued to increase. However, terms related to green energy technology, which this study identified for searching projects and papers, were used in only 19.3% of the titles and abstracts of funded papers. This suggests that more than 80% of papers are less likely related to the development of green energy technologies. However, it is too early to argue that they are not related to green energy technology, and the indirect relationship between them should also be considered. In particular, since many papers have been published by universities and received funding as basic research, they did not have to be directly linked to the industrialization that the mission desired.

Analysis of the research topics of funded papers was not covered in this study. However, to analyze the extent to which the outcomes of funded research have relevance to the mission, an in-depth investigation of the structure of research topics and their relationships with technology fields should be made in follow-up studies.

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